

NASA's Earth Science Data Systems

A Stewardship Strategy and Action Plan for NASA Earth Science Data Systems Machine Learning Training Datasets

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A Stewardship Strategy and Action Plan for NASA Earth Science Data Systems Machine Learning Training Datasets

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1. INTRODUCTION

Emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) bring about new types of data products and designated user communities. Stewardship processes and capabilities need to be defined and developed to better manage the new types of data products and serve the designated user communities.

To improve and maximize NASA Earth science AI/ML capabilities, the Earth Science Data Systems (ESDS) strategic plan has established the following five goals for the ESDS program (ESDS 2021):

- Goal 1: Augment scientific data stewardship processes;
- Goal 2: Maximize information and knowledge discovery capabilities;
- Goal 3: Enable sharing and interoperability of Earth science AI training data and models;
- Goal 4: Increase engagement with commercial, academic, other agency, and international partners; and
- Goal 5: Foster AI expertise within the program.

NASA's open data and information policy mandates that all NASA scientific information funded by the Science Mission Directorate (SMD) needs to be freely available and openly shared (NASA 2021), where scientific information includes publications, data, and software created in the pursuit of scientific knowledge.

NASA funded projects such as the 2019 Advancing Collaborative Connections for Earth System Science (ACCESS) Program¹ will be generating new training datasets for ML. However, NASA does not currently have established processes and capability to catalog and provide access to these forthcoming ML training datasets, let alone their associated models.

In response to the above goals and in support of the NASA open data and information policy, a general strategy and action plan for effective stewardship of NASA ESDS ML training datasets has been developed by a team of experts with extensive experience in ML modeling, training dataset production, scientific data management and stewardship, NASA Earth science systems and tools including the Common Metadata Repository (CMR), and cataloging of ML training datasets and models.

The ML training data strategy and action plan aims to:

- Ensure the stewardship and quality of NASA ML training datasets;
- Support open-source science and accelerate ML for Earth science by promoting open sharing of high-quality training datasets and associated benchmark models; and

¹ <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esds/competitive-programs/access>

- Enhance the value of NASA ML training datasets by improving their findability, accessibility, interoperability, and (re)usability (aka, FAIR).

As the result of this team effort, the ESDS ML training dataset short-term and long-term strategies have been developed for NASA to implement. These strategies will be refined through feedback from the NASA Earth science community.

The short-term strategy is for NASA to:

- Provide cataloging and search capability for existing and forthcoming NASA ML training datasets, integrating existing NASA tools and services (e.g., CMR-STAC; Earthdata Search Portal) with ML training data catalog(s) hosted by external partners, e.g., ML Hub by Radiant Earth Foundation, which is funded by the ACCESS-2019 announcement to advance an open-access repository for Earth observation training data.

The long-term strategy is for NASA to:

- Develop and implement capabilities to provide stewardship services (preservation, access and content improvement) to NASA ML training datasets, that are on par with other NASA datasets, for the designated ML community and general public at large;
- Develop and implement capabilities for search and discovery to facilitate access and (re)use of NASA ML training datasets and associated models; and
- Define processes and provide guidelines to maximize the transparency of ML algorithms and the research software used to develop ML training datasets, capturing relevant uncertainties and labeling biases in the process.

The rest of the document provides additional relevant or supporting information. In particular, the main terms used in this document are defined in Section 2. The motivation and purpose of developing an ESDS strategy and action plan for NASA SMD-funded ML training datasets are described in Section 3, along with the scope of the document. Section 4 outlines the current state of ML in Earth science and geosciences as well as in NASA. This is followed by a brief discussion of the quality considerations for training datasets in Section 5. Workflows for training dataset preparation, metadata curation, and cataloging/publication are described in Section 6. The short- and long-term strategies are presented in Section 7 with action plans and recommended practices toward meeting those strategies, leveraging community best practices. The document ends with a summary and path forward in Section 8.

2. DEFINITIONS

Definitions of main terms used in this document are provided in this section, along with a description of Earth sciences training dataset types and examples, as well as an example of different remote sensing machine learning scenarios.

2.1. Definitions

Machine Learning (ML) is a field within computer science that trains algorithms to automatically learn features, patterns, etc. based on experiences and use of data for a particular task. It is commonly considered as a part of artificial intelligence (AI) (NASA SMD 2021; also Figure 1).

Depending on the nature of their feedback mechanism for learning, ML approaches can be broadly grouped into four categories: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi supervised, and reinforcement learning (Figure 2).

Figure 1. A non-exhaustive overview of the AI toolbox.
From: NASA SMD (2021).

Figure 2. Taxonomy of machine learning.

Source: <https://hermit-notebook.site/en/notebook/computer-sciences/artificial-intelligence/machine-learning/taxonomy-of-machine-learning/>

Supervised learning is the machine learning task of learning a function that maps an input to an output based on example input-output pairs. A supervised learning algorithm analyzes the training data and produces an inferred function, which can be used for mapping new examples (Mohri et al. 2018; Yalcin 2020).

Unsupervised learning is a type of machine learning that looks for previously undetected patterns in a dataset with no pre-existing labels and with a minimum of human supervision. As a result, unsupervised learning algorithms must first self-discover any naturally occurring patterns in that dataset (Duda et al. 2001; Yalcin 2020).

In practice, one may combine the characteristics of supervised learning and unsupervised learning to form an alternative approach known as semi-supervised learning. *Semi-supervised learning* is particularly useful when dealing with a small amount of labeled data with a large amount of unlabeled data available for training.

Reinforcement learning is an area of machine learning concerned with how software agents ought to take actions in an environment in order to maximize the notion of cumulative reward. Reinforcement learning differs from supervised learning in not needing labeled input/output pairs to be presented, and in not needing sub-optimal actions to be explicitly corrected (Kaelbling et al. 1996; Yalcin 2020).

ML algorithms build a model based on data, as neural networks and other AI programs require an initial set of data to act as a baseline in order to make predictions or decisions (Koza et al. 1996).

Training data is usually composed of sets of data points, each labeled to indicate that they represent some sort of feature of interest. Supervised machine learning models depend on representatively and consistently described data for specific features. Without a foundation of high-quality training data, any ML algorithm will not correctly provide suitably representative results. High-quality training datasets are also needed in testing and validating results from unsupervised machine learning.

2.2. Earth Science Training Dataset Types

For Earth sciences, data can be generally grouped into the following **four** categories:

(1) **Scalar**

- (a) Physical properties and observations (e.g., Priftis et al. 2021)
- (b) Simulated information/variables
- (c) Timeseries

(2) **Raster**

- (a) Multispectral (e.g., Ramasubramanian et al. 2019; Langevin et al. 2021)
- (b) Hyperspectral (e.g., Li et al. 2019)
- (c) Single band

(3) **Text** (e.g., Zheng et al. 2019; Ramasubramanian et al. 2020)

(4) **Other**

It is often useful to utilize physical properties and observations-based data with imagery such as hail storm detection (Pullman et al. 2019) and tropical cyclone intensity estimation (Maskey et al. 2020).

Any data type that does not fit into the first three categories is included in the *Other* category.

2.3. Remote Sensing Machine Learning Scenarios

The following remote sensing machine learning scenarios are from Peng (2021) and presented here as examples shown in Figure 3. Scenarios can be formulated at the scene level, object level, and pixel level.

- At the scene level, the scenario presented is wildfire classification and the training dataset for it contains an image and its corresponding binary (Yes/No) labels (Figure 3, left panel);

- At the object level, the scenario presented is building detection and the training dataset contains an image with polygons indicating the positions of buildings (Figure 3, middle panel); and
- At the pixel level, the scenario presented is land cover classification and the training dataset includes the Earth observation (EO) imagery and the land cover classes of each pixel ² (Figure 3, right panel).

Figure 3. Remote sensing machine learning scenarios at the scene level (left panel), object level (middle panel), and pixel level (right panel). From: Peng (2021).

3. BACKGROUND

The motivation and purpose of developing an ESDS strategy and action plan for NASA funded ML training datasets and the scope of this document are described in this section.

3.1. Motivation

Training data is a key building block of reproducible ML pipelines. New technology such as ML brings new designated user communities with unique needs for their applications. While promoting sustained investment in AI R&D, the US Executive Order 13859 (2019) called for enhanced public access to government AI data and models where appropriate to increase the value of AI R&D investment. The US Office of Management and Budget (OMB) (2020) has also stated that access to federal AI data and models must be done in a manner that is consistent with the federal laws and mandates including the Open, Public, Electronic, and Necessary Government Data Act (U.S. Public Law 115-435 2019) and Open Data Policy (OMB 2013).

² Although each pixel is assigned a class, modern ML algorithms make use of features from all pixels of the image, not only the information pertaining to the pixel. These types of algorithms are called segmentation models.

In its strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024 report, NASA SMD identified that AI/ML has yet to be fully appreciated by SMD and science disciplines (NASA Strategy Data Management Working Group 2019). In response to this report, SMD has organized a workshop and brought together “NASA science community, academic partners, and industry experts to discuss ways to accelerate the adoption of AI across NASA science divisions and foster cross-disciplinary science enabled by AI utilizing large science data archives and computing platforms” (NASA SMD 2021). The common themes emerging from the workshop include the importance of standardizing AI-ready data generation workflows, identifying and documenting best practices, and providing effective stewardship for increased sharing, trustworthiness, and reproducibility.

NASA policies, such as the Scientific Information Policy for the SMD (NASA 2021, aka SPD-41), require all NASA SMD funded data and scientific information be openly available and freely shared. NASA funded researchers such as those from the Advancing Collaborative Connections for Earth System Science (ACCESS) Program,³ are producing ML training datasets utilizing NASA Earth science data. But currently NASA does not have an existing capability to catalog and share these datasets publicly.

To align with the NASA Open-Source Science Initiative and to improve the (re)use of these training datasets and to better serve the ML community, ESDS, which oversees the life cycle of NASA’s Earth science data, needs a strategy to:

- Manage ML training datasets as an asset;
- Define a way to collect, store, manage, and describe training datasets and their provenance; and
- Provide search and access capability to these datasets.

3.2. Purpose

As mentioned in Section 1, the NASA ESDS AI/ML strategic plan⁴ establishes the following five goals for the ESDS program:

- Goal 1: Augment scientific data stewardship processes;
- Goal 2: Maximize information and knowledge discovery capabilities;
- Goal 3: Enable sharing and interoperability of Earth science AI training data and models;
- Goal 4: Increase engagement with commercial, academic, other agencies, and international partners; and
- Goal 5: Foster AI expertise within the program.

³ <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esds/competitive-programs/access>

⁴ draft available at: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1oyGpu1NPRFq9qRhySehj0auCffoceXzF/view>

This document lays out a general strategy and action plan for effective stewardship of NASA ESDS training datasets in **direct** response to goals 1 and 3 to enable or enhance access and interoperability of Earth science ML training datasets, while **supporting** goals 2 and 4.

Currently known practical examples are captured as beneficial references to both ML training dataset producers and users. They are not intended to be requirements and are not exhaustive or comprehensive. These examples lean towards supervised ML applications, reflecting the current status of Earth science ML applications and the expertises in this team. Additional practice examples for other types of ML applications may be documented in future updates of this document or a related document.

The vision of the ML training data strategy and action plan document aims to:

- Ensure the stewardship quality of NASA ML training datasets;
- Support open-source science and accelerate ML for Earth science by promoting open sharing of high-quality training datasets and benchmark ML models; and
- Enhance the value of NASA ML training datasets by improving their discovery, access, and (re)use.

The objectives of developing an ESDS ML training data strategy with an action plan, are to:

- Ensure that NASA ML training datasets are well curated, managed and stewarded;
- Ensure that NASA Earth science training datasets are findable, accessible, interoperable, and (re)usable;
- Build capacity within ESDS program elements to provide sustained stewardship of ML training datasets; and
- Promote engagement and/or contribution to community efforts for a higher level of standardization for stewardship of ML training datasets.

3.3. Scope

This document applies to the stewardship of NASA-funded training datasets that are derived from Earth observations for ML applications. The strategy and action plan will be high level with additional implementation guidelines to be developed/provided in the future.

4. CURRENT STATE OF AI/ML IN EARTH SCIENCE

AI/ML is gaining momentum in all science disciplines (Blaiszik 2022; Figure 4) including Earth science (Virts et al. 2020; Figure 5) with a large variety of potential applications (Bortnik and Camporeale 2021; also Figure 6).

Figure 4. Machine learning landscape in sciences.
Source: Blaiszik (2022).

Figure 5. Machine learning landscape in Earth sciences. The yearly number of Earth science supervised ML papers from major publishers. AMS = American Meteorological Society. IEEE = Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers. SPIE = International Society for Optics and Photonics. Source: Virts et al. (2020).

Figure 6. Potential Earth science applications of machine learning.

Source: Bortnik and Camporeale (2021).

4.1. The State of Earth AI Research

A comprehensive literature review of existing Earth AI research was carried out by Sun et al. (2022) (also shown in Table 1) with data preparation being one of the challenges during the model development stage (Figure 7).

Table 1. Earth AI literature review summary. Adapted from Sun et al. (2022).

Earth Spheres	AI Techniques*	Research Topics
Atmosphere (39)	SVM (10); RF (7); BRT (1); ANN (12); DL (17); Cubist (1)	Ozone (5); Hurricane (4); Dust (3); Wildfire (5); Drought (4); Air Quality and Pollutants (6); Precipitation (11); Dew Point (1)
Geosphere (15)	ANN (6); Hidden Markov (1); DT (1); DL (3); SVM (2); Logistic Regression (2)	Earthquake (7); Volcano (2); Mineral (1); Landslide (4); Soil Erosion (1)
Hydrology (22)	DL (5); ANN (13); SVM (5); RF (4); Cubist (2)	Water forecasting (7); Water quality (3); Groundwater (7); Rainfall-runoff (4); River sediment (1); River discharge (2)
Cryosphere (14)	DL (5); RF (4); SVM (3); DT (2)	Glacier (2); Sea ice (9); Snow (3)
Oceanography (15)	DL (10); ANN (5)	Sea surface temperature (4); Surface process (2); Eddy (7); Deep current (1); Subsurface temperature (1)
Biosphere (16)	DL (15); SVM (1)	Animal behavior (6); Microorganism (6); Plant disease (1); Agriculture (5)

- * Acronyms in Table 1 for AI techniques:
- ANN: artificial neural network
 - BRT: boosted regression trees
 - DL: deep learning
 - RF: random forest
 - SVM: support vector machine/model

Figure 7. Challenges and opportunities in Earth AI.

Source: Sun et al. (2022).

4.2. The State of NASA AI/ML Research

The adoption of machine learning in U.S Earth science federal agencies such as NASA is still lagging behind the general physical science community (Adhikari 2021; Figure 8 - top panel). Even within the same agency, there is a large diversity across different disciplines. Adhikari (2021) examined the state of AI adoption within NASA. They have found that among the five NASA divisions of Earth Science, Astrophysics, Planetary, Biophysical, Heliophysics, and the High End Computing for Science program, the Earth Science division has the highest number of AI/ML submissions (Figure 8 - bottom panel).

Figure 8. The AI/ML trend in NASA versus the general science community (top). The distribution of AI/ML publications across NASA divisions (bottom). The sudden decrease in NASA funded publications in 2021 (top) is likely to be associated with the fact that the study was published in 2021 and didn't include all papers in that year. Source: Adhikari et al. (2021).

5. QUALITY CONSIDERATION OF ML TRAINING DATA

Ensuring and maintaining good data quality is important for any dataset. However, it is extremely critical for ML training datasets because it directly impacts the response of the ML algorithms and therefore the validity or relevance of their predictive outcomes. Lack of consistency in data structures, file formats, and metadata including quality information can hinder efficiency of AI/ML activities. For example, CrowdFlower (2016) estimated that about 80% of the work by data

scientists is spent on preparing data including cleaning and organizing data because of messy data (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. A break-down of what data scientists spend the most time on.
Source: CrowdFlower (2016).

5.1. Training Data Quality Dimensions

Data quality dimension, which is a characteristic or aspect of data, varies largely depending on perspectives and types of applications (e.g., Redman 1996; Lee et al. 2002; Sidi et al. 2012). For example, Redman (1996) defined accuracy, completeness, consistency, and currency as four quality dimensions of data values, while Bruce and Hillmann (2004) identified completeness, correctness, provenance, consistency, timeliness, and accessibility as common metadata quality dimensions.

Generally speaking, important training data quality dimensions include:

- Accuracy
- Completeness
- Consistency
- Integrity
- Accessibility
- Timeliness
- Uniqueness or Relevancy
- Validity and Uncertainty

In addition, Data Readiness Cluster of Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) has included the following quality dimensions in their AI-ready data checklist (ESIP Data Readiness Cluster 2022a):

- Bias
- Provenance

Any training dataset will have some level of uncertainty/error. It is essential to report those uncertainties/errors when publishing the training dataset for downstream users including ML model developers to account for them (Elmes et al. 2020).

Community responses to the ESIP Data Readiness Cluster survey has also revealed that documentation and provenance of how training data are created is still lacking, which hinders the training data reuse (ESIP Data Readiness Cluster 2022b). For a training dataset to be reproducible, a full description of provenance is necessary. How exactly that is done is still an open discussion, but data stewards should endeavor to capture as much information as possible about all the quality dimensions listed above, ideally in a formally structured way. The following sections provide more detailed guidance.

5.2. Training Data Quality Indicators and Checks

For each quality dimension of accuracy, completeness, and consistency, the ESA AI-Ready Earth Observation (AIREO) training datasets project has designated some quality indicators with recommended checks (ICHEC/CeADAR 2021). They are useful for data producers to consider and therefore captured in Table 2.

Table 2. Training dataset quality indicators and recommended checks.
Based on: ICHEC/CeADAR (2021)

Quality Dimension	Attribute for Quality Indicator	Recommended Check
Accuracy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outliers ● Data alignment ● Labeling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check the presence of outliers ● Check spatial and temporal alignment of predictive features* and reference data** ● Check inaccurate labeling
Completeness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Schema/metadata ● Population ● Column ● Interlinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check for missing values ● Check schema completeness (there are no relevant classes and properties not represented in the schema) ● Check data size against schema ● Check class balances/distribution for outliers, and classes for under-represented classes
Consistency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Time ● Statistics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check time consistency ● Check important statistics that are relevant to the EO dataset

* *Predictive features* are variables that compose the data input of a ML model. In ML, it is typically referred to as input variables or dependent variables. In the context of EO these can be the pixel values of different spectral bands in optical data or the values of backscatter coefficients in different polarisations for SAR data.

** *Reference data*, may also be referred to as label data or target data in the ML context, is a set of measurements that accurately describe a phenomenon of interest, to be predicted as the output of a ML model. Other names for reference data in the context of EO include ground truth data or calibration/validation data.

5.3. Specific Training Data Quality Considerations

Specifically, the following quality considerations for training datasets, based on Peng (2021) from the OGC ML TD Quality Working Group (WG), may be useful for training data generation:

- It is necessary to consider the scene label correctness, image size, and degree of class balance (Figure 10); and
- It is necessary to evaluate the positional accuracy of the object label, omission of object labels, label overlap rate, etc. (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Examples of mismatched scene labeling (left) and image size (middle), and skewness of label classes (right). Source: Peng (2021).

Figure 11. Examples of offsetted positional label (left), missing label (middle), and overlapped label (right). Source: Peng (2021).

5.4. Considerations for Training Data Bias

Perhaps the most critical consideration for training data stewardship is the issue of bias. Bias is an important but difficult factor to consider when supplying training data. The concept is related to but different from uncertainty. The issue is that a small (unknown) discrepancy can be falsely amplified or mischaracterized in the black box of the machine learning process.

Things that might bias an analysis include:

- Unrepresentative data sample. Spatial representativeness is a common issue in ground reference data when it's compared to satellite observations. There is a mismatch between the spatial support of a point measurement and the spatial resolution of the satellite observation defined by the sampling grid. One example is soil moisture: the satellite pixels (SMAP satellite) are at 9km x 9km, and in situ data are point measurements (Gruber et al. 2020). Another aspect of representativeness is the data distribution. There are well-documented examples of this in social sciences, such as the infamous Amazon hiring algorithm. There are also examples in medical science. We should assume similar biases exist in natural science because of limitations of collection (oceans and poles remain under sampled), undocumented idiosyncrasies, current funding/scientific interest, etc.
- Unrepresentative classes, especially under-representation of rare but important examples/labels/features. Under-representation might also happen because features/events of interest are rarely observed using instruments or might be overwhelmed by other categories it is with, e.g., Category 5 hurricanes.
- False identifiers/signals. Artifacts in the data, those things users (or specialists) know to ignore, mask out, etc.
- Missing the point. Scientists are sometimes subject to confirmation bias and miss data or observations that may contradict what they already assume to be true. This is only human, and it is ultimately corrected through the scientific process. The concern is when ML may reinforce or exacerbate these biases.

Use of different approaches such as semi-supervised learning, transfer learning, or representation learning, could help reduce bias in the training datasets (e.g., Chakraborty et al. 2022; Kustowski et al 2020; Jahanian et al, 2021). Lakshminarayanan et al. (2017) has also demonstrated that uncertainty estimation using deep ensembles does not contribute directly towards low-bias but can help make informed decisions in a high-bias setting and increase robustness.

NASA will need to develop processes to address these issues much as it works to address other data quality issues. This will require transparency, much improved tracking, and documenting data and quality assessment provenance. Community guidelines on making quality information of individual datasets FAIR (Peng et al. 2022) may be helpful to ML training dataset producers

and stewards. Ensuring and improving the quality of ML training datasets will require humans in the loop and oversight.

6. TRAINING DATASET CREATION AND PUBLICATION WORKFLOWS

Examples of high-level workflows for training dataset creation and publication are described in this section. Again, they lean towards supervised learning. There are many more details when one actually goes through these processes. Therefore, a “how-to” handbook may need to be developed.

6.1. Idealized ML Process

Machine learning processes may vary depending on types of applications. However, at a high level, a ML process can be generalized into three phases according to Ramachandran (2021) as shown in Figure 12:

- i. Preparatory phase;
- ii. Model building and training phase; and
- iii. Model testing and deployment phase.

Data curation occurs in the preparation phase. However, the quality of the curated data will influence the quality of the model as well as model performance.

Figure 12. A schematic diagram showing an idealized ML process.

Source: Ramachandran (2021).

6.2. Training Dataset Preparation Workflow

A basic ML training dataset preparation workflow can be further defined into five phases as shown in Figure 12 using imagery data as an example:

- i. Define problem;
- ii. Identify features and data source;

- iii. Create a ground truth, which is a combination of labels and raw data which will later be processed and used to create the training dataset;
- iv. Preprocess; and
- v. Create a stratified⁵ training dataset.

Examples for each of five phases are also provided in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Preparation workflow diagram for machine learning imagery training datasets. Based on: Maskey et al. (2020). ImageLabeller is an IMPACT developed tool that facilitates the creation and management of labeled Earth science images.⁶

Some of the basic concerns for producing ML training dataset include:⁷

- Training, validation, and test data are partially or completely overlapping;
- Training dataset is too small to capture the full complexity of the underlying distribution;
- Validation and test datasets are too small to provide a stable estimate of the model's generalization power;
- Training, validation and test sets are not representative of the problem domain due to, e.g., presence of high noise levels, imbalanced classes, or large chunks of similar (redundant) data points; and
- Data is not released to the public in an accessible and findable way (Gabelica et al. 2022).

To overcome those concerns, a set of community guidelines on ML data preparation has been developed (Walsh et al. 2021) and captured below:⁸

⁵ Stratification, or cross-validation is a model evaluation technique which involves splitting data into groups, namely training, validation and testing sets.

⁶ <https://impact.earthdata.nasa.gov/labeller/>

⁷ From: <https://dome-ml.org/>

⁸ <https://dome-ml.org/guidelines>

- Data size and distribution is representative of the domain;
- Independence of optimization (training) and evaluation (testing) sets;
- Release data preferably using appropriate long-term repositories, including training, testing, and validation splits; and
- Clear statement that evaluation sets were not used for feature selection, pre-processing steps, or parameter tuning.

6.3. Metadata Curation Workflow

In addition to the normal metadata associated with any dataset, there are some metadata elements such as class or feature labeling and annotations that are unique to ML training datasets (Figure 14).

Figure 14. ESA AIREO training dataset specification and workflow.

Source: ICHEC/CeADAR (2021).

Building on FAIR Guiding Principles defined by Wilkinson et al. (2016), ESA AIREO training dataset specification document provides a common structure for FAIR EO training datasets (ICHEC/CeADAR 2021).

The list below highlights relevant features in the AIREO training dataset (TDS) (ICHEC/CeADAR 2021; Le et al. 2021):

- Captured data provenance and processing history;
- Paired (reference data and EO features) and unpaired TDS;
- STAC (cloud-native data) metadata and cataloging specification;
- Defined critical metadata attributes for TDS;
- Enabled data format independence by using a JSON STAC-compatible complement to the source training dataset;
- Self-explanatory (AI-ready);

- Proposed structured quality assurance approaches with automatically generated quality indicators (quality indicator metadata); and
- Granularity considered: collection, dataset, and measurement.

6.4. Training Dataset Publication Workflow

ML training datasets are encouraged to be published via an open access ML training dataset or model repository. An example of training dataset publication workflow is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. A schematic diagram showing training dataset publication workflow. (Shard: Store single dataset distributed into multiple databases for parallel training;⁹ SSL: Semi-supervised learning)

Prior to NASA building its own capability to catalog NASA funded training datasets, it is recommended to catalog them with open access training data repositories, such as the RadiantEarth ML Hub catalog, that provide a persistent globally unique identifier such as Digital Object Identifier (DOI). It is also recommended to describe the training dataset and the processes involved in creating it in a literature article.

⁹ <https://docs.graphcore.ai/projects/tf-model-parallelism/en/latest/sharding.html>

For reference, CMR collection-level metadata and RadiantEarth ML Hub catalog metadata are listed in Tables B1 and B2 and their crosswalks are captured in Table B3.

6.5. Data File Formats and Conventions

Community standards, conventions, and formats for ML training datasets are currently lacking and still evolving. There are many generic formats such as PNG and JPEG. Below are some examples to consider for commonly used data formats (Table 3) and conventions (Table 4) in Earth science. Again, they are not intended to be exhaustive and will require frequent updating. In practice, one may need to deal with multiple formats. For example, in smoke detection, the source data files may be in NetCDF. From which, band values may be extracted as a NumPy¹⁰ array before training/validation/testing. The inferences also make use of the original file metadata for visualization.

There are numerous national and international activities such as those by the OGC SampleML for AI/ML Standards Working Group (SWG),¹¹ RDA FAIR4ML Interest Group,¹² and ESIP AI-Ready Data Cluster,¹³ even if those activities are still in a fairly preliminary stage. This is one of the areas that NASA should monitor closely or participate in to leverage or contribute to these community activities and allow for early adoption of community standards once developed.

Table 3. Data format standards common for AI/ML practitioners.

Data File Format	Description	Specifications
GeoTIFF	<p>GeoTIFF is a format extension for storing georeference and geocoding information in a TIFF 6.0 compliant raster file by tying a raster image to a known model space or map projection.</p> <p>GeoTIFF is a NASA approved data format.¹⁴</p>	<p>GeoTIFF, Revision 1.0: http://geotiff.maptools.org/spec/contents.html</p> <p>OGC GeoTIFF Standard, Revision 1.1: https://www.ogc.org/standards/geotiff</p>
Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG)	<p>A Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG) is a regular GeoTIFF file, aimed at being hosted on a HTTP file server, with an internal organization that enables more efficient workflows on the cloud.</p>	<p>https://www.cogeo.org/</p>

¹⁰ NumPy is a library for the Python programming language: <https://numpy.org/>

¹¹ <https://www.ogc.org/pressroom/pressreleases/4449>

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/defining-fair-machine-learning-ml>

¹³ https://wiki.esipfed.org/Data_Readiness

¹⁴ <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esdis/eso/standards-and-references#data-formats>

NetCDF-4	<p>NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) is a set of software libraries and self-describing, machine-independent data formats that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data.¹⁵</p> <p>NetCDF-4 is a NASA approved data format.</p>	<p>The Unidata Program Center supports and maintains netCDF programming interfaces for C, C++, Java, and Fortran.</p> <p>Programming interfaces are also available for Python, IDL, MATLAB, R, Ruby, and Perl.</p> <p>https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/</p>
GeoJSON	<p>GeoJSON is a geospatial data interchange format based on JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) (Butler et al. 2016).</p>	<p>https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc7946</p>

Table 4. Convention Standards Common for AI/ML Practitioners

Convention	Description	Specifications
STAC	The SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification provides a common language to describe a range of geospatial information, so it can more easily be indexed and discovered.	https://stacspec.org/
STAC Label Extension	This extension defines metadata for cataloging labeled datasets (pairs of label and source data). In particular, the label extension captures a relationship between a label asset and a source asset in each item of the catalog (Duckworth and Cheipesh 2021a).	https://github.com/stac-extensions/label
STAC ML-Model Extension	This extension introduces metadata required to catalog a geospatial machine learning model (Duckworth and Cheipesh 2021b). The development of this was led by the Radiant Earth Foundation team as part of their ACCESS-2019 project.	https://github.com/stac-extensions/ml-model
CF	The climate and forecast (CF) metadata convention provides a definitive description of what the data in each variable represents, and the spatial and temporal properties of the data to support processing and sharing of NetCD files.	http://cfconventions.org/
SampleML	New sample markup language for AI/ML standards under-development by OGC	OGC on-going activity: https://www.ogc.org/pressroom

¹⁵ <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>

	SampleML SWG.	/pressreleases/4449
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6.6. Artifacts to Consider for Reproducible ML Training Dataset

AI/ML enables new ways of extracting new information and gaining new knowledge from data. In addition to open data, software, process, and results should also be open for reproducible data. Open and reproducible data is the first step towards open and reproducible science (Ramachandran et al. 2021).

Although the artifacts listed below are not yet stored in a systematic manner and are not always shared, they are important to consider for a reproducible ML training dataset during each phase of the ML process as shown in Figure 12. Examples for enabling open access for various artifacts are provided if relevant, based on Ramachandran (2021).

Data preparation phase:

- Feature engineering code
 - *Github, GitLab, BitBucket, etc.*
- Training datasets
 - *Radiant MLHub*
 - *AWS OpenData Programs*
 - *Datasets available through pytorch datasets¹⁶ and tensorflow¹⁷*

Model building and training phase:

- ML models
 - *Model Zoos¹⁸ such as Huggingface¹⁹ or equivalent repository*
 - *Radiant MLHub*
- ML model initialization
 - *Reproducible Initial Model configuration, random seeds for non-deterministic processes*
- ML Experiment tracking and management
 - *Jupyter Notebooks, JupyterHub, for tracking flow of training*
 - *WandB, comet.ai, Neptune.ai, MLFlow, Tensorboard, SageMaker Studio*

Model deployment and testing phase:

- Repeatable deployment pipeline
 - *Model code should be deposited in GitHub, GitLab, or equivalent repository. Uploading the model in the known location, e.g., cloud resources where they*

¹⁶ <https://pytorch.org/vision/stable/datasets.html>

¹⁷ <https://www.tensorflow.org/resources/models-datasets>

¹⁸ <https://modelzoo.co/>

¹⁹ <https://huggingface.co/models>

could be utilized such as AWS S3 buckets.

- Periodic Performance Evaluation Metrics/Approach
 - *Model Zoos*
 - *GitHub*
 - *Docker images*

Similar to the case of training datasets, once a benchmark model is released, it is recommended to describe technical details on how the benchmark model was trained/prepared in a literature publication. It is possible to describe the benchmark model and associated training dataset in a single paper.

7. STRATEGY AND ACTION PLAN

As mentioned previously, NASA does not currently have the capability to catalog and provide access to existing and forthcoming NASA-funded ML training datasets. Both short- and long-term strategies are therefore needed. They are outlined below along with an action plan and recommended practices to help implement the strategy.

7.1. Short-term Strategy and Action Plan

- Provide cataloging and search capability for NASA machine learning training datasets, integrating the existing NASA tools and services (e.g., CMR-STAC; Earthdata Search) with ML training data catalog(s) and models hosted by external partners (e.g., MLHub by Radiant Earth Foundation)

Radiant MLHub²⁰ is a cloud-based, open access benchmark repository of machine learning Earth observation training datasets and models, built on the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) metadata standards, partially funded by NASA via the ACCESS-2019 announcements.

It is recommended that data producers who wish to publish their ML training datasets via an external repository such as ML Hub engage with the repository early to get familiar with the data cataloging and publication process as well as data structure and catalog metadata requirements.

Action plan:

- Catalog the existing Earth science ML training datasets that are funded by NASA, including those to be produced by on-going NASA programs such as Advancing Collaborative Connections for Earth System Science (ACCESS) Program,²¹ collaborating with external partners (e.g., Radiant MLHub);
- Provide information on each dataset's associated benchmark ML model;

²⁰ <https://mlhub.earth/>

²¹ <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esds/competitive-programs/access>

→ Integrate ML training data collection metadata into CMR with tags;

In addition, it is recommended to

- ◆ Utilize the OMB training data tag “usg-ai-training-data” and/or “usg-ai-testing-data” and also the topic tag “usg-artificial-intelligence” in metadata to make it easier for training datasets to be discovered and reused by the general public and across all federal agencies (both tags are established by the OMB);²² and
 - ◆ Cross-reference with the benchmark ML model.
- Provide search and discovery capabilities through the Earthdata Search portal with a link back to the ML training dataset catalog (e.g., Radiant MLHub) to access the individual datasets;²³
- Provide training data download metrics in accordance with broadly accepted community guidelines like COUNTER.²⁴

Recommended practices:

- Provide imagery training dataset with a consistent patch size (e.g., 256 x 256 pixels), and a corresponding STAC file with the reference/source image name, dates, and geographic boundary if applicable;
- Ensure consistency in labeling and annotating classes and/or features;
- Ensure comprehensiveness and degree of balance in class labeling;
- Make the benchmark ML model publicly available, e.g., on Github, or cataloged in NASA-sponsored or an open access machine learning model repository; and
- Cross-reference both training dataset and its benchmark ML model if both are publicly available, preferably using globally unique persistent identifiers.

7.2. Long-term Strategy and Action Plan

- Develop and implement capabilities to provide stewardship services (preservation, access, and content improvement) for NASA ML training datasets that are on par with other NASA datasets for the designated ML community and general public;
 - Under the circumstances, NASA may designate an external repository to host ML training datasets and models.
- Develop and implement capabilities for search and discovery to facilitate access and (re)use of NASA ML training datasets;

²² https://code.gov/assets/data/ai_inventory-guidance.pdf

²³ Radiant MLHub allows users to search the catalog with any type of property (time, spatial bound, keywords, title, doi, etc) with the API. It also offers the capability of browsing training datasets by application types on the website as well as a faceted search for a specific region, or application, sensor, and ML model type.

²⁴ <https://www.projectcounter.org/code-of-practice-rd-sections/foreword/>

- Develop controlled vocabularies for AI/ML training dataset; and
- Enhance or develop methods for tracking usage of training datasets in research, applications, and education;
- Define new processes if needed and provide guidelines for following existing NASA data and metadata standards for ML training datasets;
- Define processes and provide guidelines to maximize the transparency of research software²⁵ used to develop ML training datasets and capture relevant information on data uncertainties and labeling biases;
- Define processes and provide guidelines on including all relevant information associated with the benchmark ML model if appropriate;
- Monitor or participate in the development of relevant community standards (e.g., OGC, RDA, ESIP); and
- Adopt relevant emerging community standards.

Action plan:

- Build capacity to create, curate, and publish high-quality ML training datasets with comprehensive metadata and labellings that are FAIR.

When producing training datasets,

- ◆ Dataset producers should:
 - Be familiar with and follow NASA documents:
 - a.** Data Product Development Guide (DPDG), a high-level strategic guide that includes specifics on formats and tools (Ramapriyan and Leonard 2020) or at least the quick-start guide to the DPDG (Ramapriyan and Leonard 2021);
 - b.** Preservation Content Specifications (PCS) (Ramapriyan et al. 2021); and
 - c.** PCS Implementation Guidelines (Ramapriyan et al. 2022);
 - Provide comprehensive descriptions of the algorithm and workflow of training data creation;
 - Ensure enough data for training, testing, and validation split;
 - Take the quality considerations for training datasets described above into account when creating labels;
 - Fully describe data in accordance with the documents in Item **a.** above under the first item and include detailed quality information as described in section 5; and

²⁵ Research Software include source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the research process or for research purpose, as defined by the RDA FAIR Research Software Working Group (Chue Hong et al. 2021).

- Use standards, conventions, and data formats that are common to AI/ML practitioners, being mindful of community needs and evolving data file formats (see Table 2 for some initial items to consider).

When managing training datasets,

- ◆ Data repositories:
 - Be familiar with Preservation Content Specifications (PCS) which provides guidelines on practices for long-term preservation (Ramapriyan et al. 2021) and PCS Implementation Guidelines (Ramapriyan et al. 2022);
 - Develop capability for ML training dataset ingest, metadata curation, and dataset release, in collaboration with ESDIS;
 - Provide necessary staff training for long-term preservation and effective stewardship of NASA ML training datasets, engaging data staff directly in ML projects; and
 - Develop capability to effectively serve ML training datasets to their domain communities.
- ◆ ESDIS:
 - Support and facilitate GCMD AI/ML keywords development to help ensure AI/ML training data and related digital resources, including benchmark ML models, are described in a consistent manner for improved discovery and interoperability;
 - Support and facilitate long-term preservation and stewardship of ML training datasets, along with appropriate metadata and labellings and information about the benchmark ML models if appropriate;
 - Support and facilitate participation and/or adoption of emerging community ML training data standards; and
 - Support and facilitate data repository staff training in managing ML training datasets, metadata, and associated contextual information.
- Develop and implement an integrated workflow to catalog training datasets with search and discovery capabilities, including necessary enhancement to:
 - ◆ Search and discovery infrastructure (new or augmenting); and
 - ◆ Dataset-level CMR metadata:
 - Identify and implement changes to the CMR schema;
 - Integrate STAC and the label extension into CMR/UMM; and
 - Provide consistent links between training datasets and their associated benchmark ML models.
- Develop guidance and requirements for external ML training dataset and model repositories if such a service cannot be provided by NASA at the time:

- ◆ A guide document for competence of repositories that are aligned with NASA's requirements should be provided to the designated external repository;
- ◆ Level of Service agreement should be developed jointly to specifically define the services to be provided by the designated repository.

→ Improve framework and workflow for capturing ML training dataset provenance.

The quality considerations and recommendations for training datasets described in the previous section and recommended practices for the short-term strategy should also be part of the long-term strategy and action with additional guidelines developed specifically for the NASA ML community.

8. SUMMARY AND PATH FORWARD

This document lays out a general strategy and action plan for NASA Earth Science Data Systems ML training datasets in accordance with NASA's strategic goals. The document has been developed by a team of cross-disciplinary experts, leveraging their expertise and knowledge of leading community practices.

The **short-term strategy** is for NASA to provide cataloging and search capability for NASA ML training datasets, integrating the existing NASA tools and services (e.g., CMR-STAC; Earthdata Search) with ML training data catalog(s) hosted by external partners (e.g., ML Hub by Radiant Earth Foundation).

The **long-term strategy** is for NASA to:

- Develop and implement capabilities to provide stewardship services (preservation, access, and content improvement) to NASA ML training datasets, that are on par with other NASA datasets, for the designated ML community and general public at large;
- Develop and implement capabilities for search and discovery to facilitate access and (re)use of NASA ML training datasets; and
- Define processes and provide guidelines to maximize the transparency of research software used to develop ML training datasets and capture relevant uncertainties and labeling biases.

Capacity building in both infrastructure and staff will be essential in enhancing access, (re)use, and interoperability of training datasets and supporting the adoption of ML in NASA and a wider community. Having a few well-established training datasets is critical to the education process and it is useful for them to be built into common ML toolkits such as those in scikit-learn.²⁶ It is therefore recommended to establish key benchmarks with well-understood training datasets,

²⁶ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/datasets.html>

working with data producers or providers, that can be used for educational purposes, including training for current staff as well as future workforce.

These short- and long-term strategies and action plans will be refined through feedback from the NASA Earth science community.

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Table 5. Team members and their roles, responsibilities, and subject areas.

Name	Role	Responsibility & Subject Areas
Manil Maskey	ESDS & IMPACT AI/ML Strategist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project lead - Guidance on the scope - Liaison across disciplines of team members
Ge Peng	UAH/IMPACT Data Stewardship Subject Matter Expert (SME)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team lead - MLTD quality metadata - MLTD management and stewardship
Iksha Gurung	UAH/IMPACT ML Lead	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ML training datasets creation/curation - MLTD publication and sharing steps - Benchmarking best practices - ML training data types and examples
Muthukumaran Ramasubramanian	UAH/IMPACT ML Tools Support	
Shubhankar Gahlot	UAH/IMPACT ML SME	
Mark Parsons	UAH/IMPACT Data Stewardship SME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ML training data discovery and interoperability - MLTD management and stewardship
Chris Lynnes	EOSDIS System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ESDIS perspective

	Architect, retired	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data systems - Guidance on CMR integration
Vincent Inverso	ESDIS strategist for ML	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ESDIS perspective - Analysis-ready data in the cloud - Usage-based discovery
Sara Lubkin	ESDIS/PO.DAAC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ESDIS liaison for IMPACT - ACCESS Project - ESCO perspective
Nicholas (Nic) Doty	ESDIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data ingest and archiving in the cloud - Cloud optimized data
Dana Ostrenga	ESDIS/GSFC Data management Architect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ESDIS perspective - Data Observing Systems
Mark S. Reese	CMR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CMR perspective - CMR search and discovery - Contribute to team discussions
Valerie Dixon	CMR Lead	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CMR-RandiantEarth ML Hub integration
Seyed Hamed Alemohammad	Principal Investigator Open Imagery Network, Inc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidance on Radiant MLHub catalog metadata for training datasets and models - Crosswalks between CMR and Radiant MLHub
Jerika Christman	Project coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team meetings coordination and administration support

REFERENCES

- Adhikari, S., M. Ramasubramanian, I. Gurung, A. Acharya, and M. Maskey, 2021: Trend Analysis of AI/ML Tools and Services in NASA. IN31A-08. *2021 AGU Fall Meeting*, New Orleans, LA, 13-17 December 2021. ePoster available online at: <https://agu2021fallmeeting-agu.ipostersessions.com/default.aspx?s=D7-8E-37-98-53-9E-FE-83-72-62-CA-25-14-09-98-A4&guestview=true>
- Blaiszik, B., 2022: Charting ML Publications in Sciences. Version: February 2022. Available at: https://github.com/blaiszik/ml_publication_charts
- Bortnik, J. and E. Camporeale, 2021: Ten ways to apply machine learning in Earth and space sciences, *Eos*, 102, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021EO160257>. Published on 29 June 2021.
- Bruce, T. R. and D. I. Hillmann, 2004: The Continuum of Metadata Quality: Defining, Expressing, Exploiting. In: *Metadata in Practice*. Cornell University Library: ALA Editions. Available at <https://hdl.handle.net/1813/7895>
- Chakraborty, J., S. Majumder, and H. Tu, 2022: Fair-SSL: Building fair ML Software with less data. *Equitable Data and Technology (FairWare '22)*, May 9, 2022, Pittsburgh, PA, USA. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2111.02038.pdf>
- Chue Hong, N. P., D. S. Katz, M. Barker, A.-L. Lamprecht, C. Martinez, F. E. Psomopoulos, J. Harrow, L. J. Castro, M. Gruenpeter, P. A. Martinez, T. Honeyman, and others, 2021: FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles). *Research Data Alliance*. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00065>

- CrowdFlower, 2016: 2016 Data Science Report. Available at: http://visit.figure-eight.com/rs/416-ZBE-142/images/CrowdFlower_DataScienceReport_2016.pdf
- Duckworth, J. and E. Cheipesh, 2021a: Discoverable and Reusable ML Workflows for Earth Observation (Part 1) - Using STAC to catalog machine learning training data. Version: 12 July 2021. Available at: <https://medium.com/radiant-earth-insights/discoverable-and-reusable-ml-workflows-for-earth-observation-part-1-e198507b5eaa>
- Duckworth, J. and E. Cheipesh, 2021b: Discoverable and Reusable ML Workflows for Earth Observation (Part 2) - Describing ML Models with the Geospatial Machine Learning Model Catalog (GMLMC). Version: 12 July 2021. Available at: <https://medium.com/radiant-earth-insights/discoverable-and-reusable-ml-workflows-for-earth-observation-part-2-ebe2b4812d5a>
- Duda, R. O., P. E. Hart, and D. G. Stork, 2001: Unsupervised Learning and Clustering. *Pattern classification* (2nd ed.). Wiley. ISBN: 0-471-05669-3.
- Elmes A., H. Alemohammad, R. Avery, K. Caylor, J.R. Eastman and others, 2020: Accounting for Training Data Error in Machine Learning Applied to Earth Observations. *Remote Sensing*. 12(6):1034. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12061034>
- ESIP Data Readiness Cluster, 2022a: Checklist to Examine AI-readiness for Open Environmental Datasets. ESIP. *Figshare*. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.19983722.v1>
- ESIP Data Readiness Cluster, 2022b: Summary report of community survey on AI-ready data.
- ESDS (Earth Science Data Systems), 2021: NASA Earth Science Data Systems Artificial Intelligence Strategy. Draft. Available upon request.
- Gabelica, M., R. Bojic, and L. Puljak, 2022: Many researchers were not compliant with their published data sharing statement: a mixed-methods study. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2022.05.019>
- Grubera, A., G. De Lannoy, C. Albergel, A. Al-Yaari, L. Brocca, J.-C. Calvet, A. Colliander, M. Cosh, W. Crow, W. Dorigo, C. Draper, M. Hirschi, Y. Kerr, A. Konings, W. Lahoz, K. McColl, C. Montzka, J. Muñoz-Sabater, J. Peng, R. Reichle, P. Richaume, C. Rüdiger, T. Scanlon, R. van der Schalie, J.-P. Wigneron, W. Wagner, 2020: Validation practices for satellite soil moisture retrievals: What are (the) errors? *Remote Sensing of Environ.*, 244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.111806>
- ICHEC (Irish Centre for High-End Computing)/CeADAR (Centre for Applied Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence), 2021: AIREO training dataset specification. Document ID: AIREO DEL-03. Version: 1.0 16-Aug-2021. Available at: <https://www.aireo.net/aireo-training-dataset-specification/>
- Jahanian, A., Puig, X., Tian, Y., & Isola, P., 2021: Generative models as a data source for multiview representation learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.05258. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2106.05258.pdf>
- Kaelbling, L. P., M. L. Littman, and A. W. Moore, 1996: Reinforcement Learning: A Survey. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*. 4. <https://doi.org/10.1613/jair.301>
- Koza, J. R., F. H. Bennett, D. Andre, and M. A. Keane, 1996: Automated Design of Both the Topology and Sizing of Analog Electrical Circuits Using Genetic Programming. *Artificial Intelligence in Design '96*. Springer, Dordrecht. pp. 151–170. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-0279-4_9
- Kustowski, B. L., J. A. Gaffney, B. K. Spears, G. J. Anderson, J. J. Thiagarajan and R. Anirudh, 2020: Transfer Learning as a Tool for Reducing Simulation Bias: Application to

- Inertial Confinement Fusion, in *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, 48, DOI: [10.1109/TPS.2019.2948339](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPS.2019.2948339)
- Lakshminarayanan, B., D. Tran, and J. Snoek, 2017: Introduction to Uncertainty in Deep Learning. Slides. Available at: <https://www.gatsby.ucl.ac.uk/~balaji/balaji-uncertainty-talk-cifar-dlrl.pdf>
- Langevin, S., C. Bethune, P. Horne, S. Kramer, J. Gleason, B. Johnson, E. Barnett, F. Husain, and A. Bradley, 2021: Useable machine learning for Sentinel-2 multispectral satellite imagery, *Proc. SPIE 11862, Image and Signal Processing for Remote Sensing XXVII*, 118620F (12 September 2021). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2599951>
- Le, Q., M. Spence, I. Preet, N. Moran, A. Warde, M. Fernandez J. Hanafin, A. McKinstry, V. Kannan, O. Boydell, 2021: AIREO EO training dataset specification best practice guidelines. Document ID: AIREO DEL-04. Version: 1.0 16-Aug-2021. Available from: <https://www.aireo.net/aireo-training-dataset-best-practice-guidelines/>
- Li, S., W. Song, L. Fang, Y. Chen, P. Ghamisi, and J. Benediktsson, 2019: Deep Learning for Hyperspectral Image Classification: An Overview. *IEEE Transactions On Geoscience And Remote Sensing*, 57. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2019.2907932>
- Maskey, M., R. Ramachandran, M. Ramasubramanian, I. Gurung, B. Freitag, A. Kaulfus, D. Bollinger, D. Cecil, and J. J. Miller, 2020: Deepti: Deep Learning-based Tropical Cyclone Intensity Estimation System. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*. 13, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTARS.2020.3011907>
- Maskey, M., H. Alemohammad, K. J. Murphy, and R. Ramachandran, 2020: Advancing AI for Earth science: A data systems perspective, *Eos*, 101, doi: 10.1029/2020EO151245.
- Mohri, M., A. Rostamizadeh, and A. Talwalkar, 2018: Foundations of Machine Learning. Second ed. The MIT Press. ISBN: 9780262039406.
- NASA. 2021: Scientific Information policy for the Science Mission Directorate. SMD Policy Document SPD-41. Version: August 4, 2021. Available at: <https://science.nasa.gov/science-red/s3fs-public/atoms/files/Scientific%20Information%20policy%20SPD-41.pdf>
- NASA Strategy Data Management Working Group, 2019: Science Mission Directorate's Strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024. Version: December 17, 2019. Available at: https://science.nasa.gov/science-red/s3fs-public/atoms/files/SDMWG%20Strategy_Final.pdf
- NASA, 2021: Scientific Information policy for the Science Mission Directorate. SMD Policy Document SPD-41. Version: August 4, 2021. Available at: <https://science.nasa.gov/science-red/s3fs-public/atoms/files/Scientific%20Information%20policy%20SPD-41.pdf>
- NASA SMD (Science Mission Directorate), 2021: NASA SMD AI Workshop Report. Version: Sept 2021. Available at: [https://science.nasa.gov/science-red/s3fs-public/atoms/files/NASA%20SMD%20AI%20Workshop%202021%20\(spreads\).pdf](https://science.nasa.gov/science-red/s3fs-public/atoms/files/NASA%20SMD%20AI%20Workshop%202021%20(spreads).pdf)
- Peng, G., C. Lacagnina, R. R. Downs, A. Ganske, H. K. Ramapriyan, I. Ivánová, L. Wyborn, D. Jones, L. Bastin, C.-I. Shie and D. F. Moroni, 2022: Global Community Guidelines for Documenting, Sharing, and Reusing Quality Information of Individual Digital Datasets. *Data Science Journal*. doi: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2022-008>
- Peng, Y., 2021: Quality considerations for training DML-AI. *SciDataCon 2021*. 19 October 2021. Slides are available at: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1a08USZWN4aAT8K5bpC-xVoDAsncRwOs5/view?usp=sharing>

- Pullman, M., I. Gurung, M. Maskey, R. Ramachandran, and S. Christopher, 2019: Applying Deep Learning to Hail Detection: A Case Study. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*. 57, doi:[10.1109/TGRS.2019.2931944](https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2019.2931944)
- Priftis, G., A. S. Kaulfus, M. Ramasubramanian, S. Gahlot, M. Khatri, I. Gurung, M. Maskey, R. Ramachandran, and S. A. Christopher, 2021: A Novel Machine Learning Method for Surface PM_{2.5} Estimations from Geostationary Satellites. *2021 AGU Fall Meeting*. Abstract: A25J-1812. Available at: <https://agu.confex.com/agu/fm21/meetingapp.cgi/Paper/889784>
- Ramachandran, R., 2021: Open Science and AI. *2021 AGU Fall Meeting*. Virtual.
- Ramachandran, R., K. Bugbee, and K. Murphy, 2021: From Open Data to Open Science. *Earth and Space Sci.*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EA001562>
- Ramapriyan, H. K., and P. J. T. Leonard, 2020: Data Product Development Guide (DPDG) for Data Producers version 1. NASA Earth Science Data and Information System Standards Office, Updated: 21 October 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5067/DOC/ESO/RFC-041VERSION1>
- Ramapriyan, H. K., and P. J. T. Leonard, 2021: Quick Start Guide to the EOSDIS Data Product Development Guide for Data Producers version 1. NASA Earth Science Data and Information System Standards Office, Publication Date 2021-06-23. https://doi.org/10.5067/DOC/ESO/DPDG_QSG_VERSION1
- Ramapriyan, H. J. Moses, and D. Smith, 2021: NASA Earth Science Data Preservation Content Specification. NASA GSFC. Version: 0.95, April 22, 2021. Under NASA Standards Office review.
- Ramapriyan, H., J. Moses, and D. Smith, 2022: Preservation Content Implementation Guidance. Version: 1.0. <https://doi.org/10.5067/DOC/ESO/RFC-042>
- Ramasubramanian, M., A. Kaulfus, M. Maskey, R. Ramachandran, I. Gurung, B. Freitag, and S. Christopher, 2019: Pixel level smoke detection model with deep neural network, *Proc. SPIE 11155, Image and Signal Processing for Remote Sensing XXV*, 1115515 (7 October 2019). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2532562>
- Ramasubramanian, M., H. Muhammad, I. Gurung, M. Maskey, and R. Ramachandran, 2020: ES2Vec: Earth Science Metadata Keyword Assignment using Domain-Specific Word Embeddings. *IEEE 2020 SoutheastCon*. Virtual. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/SoutheastCon44009.2020.9249743>
- Redman, C. T. 1996: Data quality of the information age. Artech House, Boston. 303 pp.
- Sidi, F., P. S. Panahy, L. S. Affendey, M. A. Jabar, H. Ibrahim, and A. Mustapha, 2012: Data quality: A survey of data quality dimensions. *2012 International Conference on Information Retrieval & Knowledge Management*, 13-15 March 2012, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/6204995>
- Sun, Z., L. Sandoval, R. Crystal-Ornelas, S. M. Mousavi and others, 2022: A review of Earth Artificial Intelligence. *Computer and Geosciences*, 159. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2022.105034>
- Thompson, D. and P. G. Brodrick, 2021: Realizing Machine Learning's Promise in Geoscience Remote Sensing. *Eos*, 102, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021EO160605>. Published on 08 July 2021.
- US Executive Order 13859, 2019: Maintaining American Leadership in Artificial Intelligence. February 13, 2019. Available at: <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2019-02-14/pdf/2019-02544.pdf>

- US OMB (Office of Management and Budget), 2013: Open Data Policy: Managing Information as an Asset. Document ID: M-13-13. Version: May 9, 2013. Available at: <https://www.whitehouse.gov/sites/whitehouse.gov/files/omb/memoranda/2013/m-13-13.pdf>
- US OMB, 2020: Guidance for Regulation of Artificial Intelligence Applications. Document ID: M-21-06. Version: November 17, 2020. Available at: <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/M-21-06.pdf>
- US Public Law 115-435, 2019: Title II—Open, Public, Electronic, and Necessary Government Data Act. Version: Jan 14, 2019. Available at: <https://www.congress.gov/115/plaws/publ435/PLAW-115publ435.pdf>
- Virts, K., A. Shirey, G. Priftis, K. Ankur, M. Ramasubramanian, H. Muhammad, A. Acharya, and R. Ramachandran, 2020: A Quantitative Analysis on the Use of Supervised Machine Learning in Earth Science. *2020 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS39084.2020.9323770>
- Walsh, I., D. Fishman, D. Garcia-Gasulla, T. Titma, G. Pollastri, The ELIXIR Machine Learning focus group, J. Harrow, F. E. Psomopoulos, and S. C.E. Tosatto, 2021: DOME: Recommendations for supervised machine learning validation in biology. Available at: <https://dome-ml.org/guidelines>
- Wilkinson, M. D., M. Dumontier, I. J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, M. Axton, A. Baak, and others 2016: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018 (2016). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Yalcin, O. G., 2020: 4 Machine Learning Approaches that Every Data Scientist Should Know. *Towards Data Science*. Version: November 15, 2021. Available at: <https://towardsdatascience.com/4-machine-learning-approaches-that-every-data-scientist-should-know-e3a9350ec0b9>
- Zheng, L., A. Albayrak, W. Teng, M. Khayat, and L. Pham, 2019: Understanding Machine Learning in Earth Science: A Natural Language Processing Approach. 2019 AGU Fall Meeting. Poster. Available at: <https://agu2019fallmeeting-agu.ipostersessions.com/Default.aspx?s=EA-5C-A6-79-75-6B-BC-C4-1B-D6-AA-DB-B8-D6-8D-6A>

APPENDIX A. ACRONYMS

AIREO	AI-Ready Earth Observations
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CeADAR	Centre for Applied Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence
CMR	Common Metadata Repository
ESA	European Space Agency
ESDS	Earth Science Data Systems
ESIP	Earth Science Information Partners
ESSC	Earth System Science Center
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite
ICHEC	Irish Centre for High-End Computing
IMPACT	Inter-Agency Implementation and Advanced Concepts Team
ML	Machine learning
MSFC	Marshall Space Flight Center
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NHC	National Hurricane Center
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SMD	Science Mission Directorate
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog

APPENDIX B. CROSSWALKS BETWEEN CMR AND ML HUB METADATA

An excel file containing elements of the collection-level unified metadata models (UMM-C) of NASA Common Metadata Repository (CMR), that of SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) collection used for RadiantEarth ML Hub catalog metadata, and crosswalks between two is provided by the Radiant team and recapitulated in Tables B1-B3, respectively.

Table B1. Elements of the collection-level unified metadata models (UMM-C) of NASA Common Metadata Repository (CMR)

Element	Definition	Required
Metadata Language	This element specifies the language used in the metadata record (i.e., English, French, Chinese, etc.).	No
Metadata Dates	This element is used to identify dates when the metadata changed in some way. This element is made of two sub-elements, Type and Date.	No
Directory Names	This element has been used historically by the GCMD internally to identify association, responsibility and/or ownership of the dataset, service or supplemental information. Note: This field only occurs in the DIF. When a DIF record is retrieved in the ECHO10 or ISO 19115 formats, this element will not be translated.	No
Entry Title	This element describes the title of the dataset described by the metadata.	Yes
DOI	This element stores the DOI (Digital Object Identifier) that identifies the dataset.	Yes
Associated DOIs	This element stores the associated DOIs that identifies associated collections or other items to this collection.	No
Abstract	This element provides a brief description of the dataset the metadata represents.	Yes
Purpose	This element contains suggested usage for the data and/or a description for why the resource exists.	No
Data Language	This element describes the language used in the preparation, storage, and description of the collection. It is the language of the collection data itself. It does not refer to the language used in the metadata record (although this may be the same language)	No
Data Dates	This element is used to identify dates when the data or resource itself changed in some way.	No
Data Center	This element is used to identify and provide contact information for the organization responsible for originating, processing, archiving, and/or distributing the dataset being described in the metadata.	Yes
Contact Group	This element is used to provide contact information for a group associated with the dataset.	No
Contact Person	This element is used to provide contact information for an individual associated with the dataset.	No
Collection Data Type	This element is used to identify the collection as a Science Quality Collection or as a non-science-quality collection such as a Near Real Time collection.	No
Processing Level	This element describes an identifier indicating the level at which the data in the collection are processed, ranging from level 0 (raw instrument data at full resolution) to level 4 (model output or analysis results).	Yes
Collection Citation	This element provides the information required to properly cite the collection in professional scientific literature.	No
Collection Progress	This element describes the production status of the dataset.	Yes

Quality	This element describes the quality of the dataset.	No
Use Constraints	This element defines how data may or may not be used to assure the protection of privacy or intellectual property. This includes license information, or any special restrictions, legal prerequisites, terms and conditions, and/or limitations on using the dataset.	No
Access Constraints	This element describes any restrictions imposed on data access. Access Constraints can be described in a free text field with the option to provide an access control list (ACL) value.	No
Archive and Distribution Information	This element and all of its sub elements allow a data provider to provide archive and distribution file information up front to an end user, to help them decide if they can use the product. The file information includes AverageFileSize - typically used for granules as well as file formats and other file information.	No
Direct Distribution Information	The direct distribution information main element allows data providers to provide users information on getting direct access to data products that are stored in the Amazon Web Service (AWS) S3 buckets when they are initially looking at a collection. The end users get information such as the S3 credentials end point, a credential documentation URL, as well as bucket prefix names, and an AWS region.	No
Publication Reference	This element describes key bibliographic citations pertaining to the collection.	No
ISO Topic Category	This element identifies the topic category (or categories) from the EN ISO 19115 Topic Category Code List that pertain to a collection.	No
Science Keywords	This element enables specification of Earth Science keywords.	Yes
Ancillary Keywords	This element allows metadata authors to provide words or phrases beyond the controlled Science Keyword vocabulary, to further describe the collection.	No
Additional Attributes	This element stores the data's distinctive attributes (i.e. attributes used to describe the unique characteristics of the resource which extend beyond those defined in this mapping).	No
Metadata Association	This element is used to identify other metadata resources that are dependent on or related to the data described by the metadata.	No
Temporal Extent	This element describes when data were acquired or collected.	No
Paleo Temporal Coverage	This element defines the time period for geologic and/or paleoclimate data. The element is predominantly used for data samples that originated prior to 01-01-0001.	No
Temporal Keywords	This element specifies a word or phrase which serves to summarize the temporal characteristics of a dataset.	No
Spatial Extent	This element describes the geographic coverage of the data.	No
Tiling Identification System	This element defines a named two-dimensional tiling system related to the collection.	No
Spatial Information	This element stores information about the reference frame from which horizontal and vertical spatial domains are measured. The horizontal reference frame includes fields for Geodetic Model, Geographic Coordinates, and Local Coordinates. The Vertical reference frame includes fields for altitudes (elevations) and depths.	No
Location Keywords	This element contains keywords that characterize the study area/region where data was collected.	No
Platform	This element describes the relevant platforms used to acquire the data.	Yes

Instrument	This element is used to register the device that measured or recorded the data, including direct human observation.	Yes
Project	This element describes the scientific endeavor(s) with which the collection is associated.	No
Related URL	This element describes any resource-related URLs that include project home pages, resource information pages, services, related data, archives/servers, metadata extensions, direct links to online software packages, web mapping services, links to images, documents, or other data.	Yes
Short Name	This element describes the dataset short name.	Yes
Version	This element describes the dataset version.	Yes
Version Description	This element describes the version of the dataset.	No

Table B2. Elements of SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) collection

Element	Type	Description
type	string	REQUIRED. Must be set to Collection to be a valid Collection.
stac_version	string	REQUIRED. The STAC version the Collection implements.
stac_extensions	[string]	A list of extension identifiers the Collection implements.
id	string	REQUIRED. Identifier for the Collection that is unique across the provider.
title	string	A short descriptive one-line title for the Collection.
description	string	REQUIRED. Detailed multi-line description to fully explain the Collection. CommonMark 0.29 syntax MAY be used for rich text representation.
keywords	[string]	List of keywords describing the Collection.
license	string	REQUIRED. Collection's license(s), either a SPDX License identifier, various if multiple licenses apply or proprietary for all other cases.
providers	[Provider Object]	A list of providers, which may include all organizations capturing or processing the data or the hosting provider. Providers should be listed in chronological order with the most recent provider being the last element of the list.
extent	Extent Object	REQUIRED. Spatial and temporal extents.
summaries	Map<string, [*]Range Object JSON Schema Object>	STRONGLY RECOMMENDED. A map of property summaries, either a set of values, a range of values or a JSON Schema.
links	[Link Object]	REQUIRED. A list of references to other documents.
assets	Map<string, Asset Object>	Dictionary of asset objects that can be downloaded, each with a unique key.
sci:doi	string	The DOI of the data, e.g. 10.1000/xyz123. This MUST NOT be a DOI's link. For all DOI names respective DOI links SHOULD be added to the links section (see chapter "Relation types").
sci:citation	string	The recommended human-readable reference (citation) to be used by publications citing the data. No specific citation style is suggested, but the citation should contain all information required to find the publication distinctively.
sci:publications	[Publication Object]	List of relevant publications referencing and describing the data.

Table B3. Crosswalks between CMR UMM-C and STAC Collection elements
(The fields that aren't required in UMM-C are shaded.)

UMM-C Field	Required?	STAC Field	Required?
<i>Metadata Language</i>	No		No
<i>Metadata Dates</i>	No		No
<i>Directory Names</i>	No		No
Entry Title	Yes	title	No
DOI	Yes	sci:doi	No
<i>Associated DOIs</i>	No	<i>sci:publications</i>	No
Abstract	Yes	description	Yes
<i>Purpose</i>	No		No
<i>Data Language</i>	No		No
<i>Data Dates</i>	No	<i>extent</i>	Yes
Data Center	Yes	providers	Yes
<i>Contact Group</i>	No	<i>providers</i>	No
<i>Contact Person</i>	No	<i>providers</i>	No
<i>Collection Data Type</i>	No		
Processing Level	Yes		No
<i>Collection Citation</i>	No	<i>sci:citation</i>	No
Collection Progress	Yes		Maybe
<i>Quality</i>	No		No
<i>Use Constraints</i>	No	<i>license</i>	Yes
<i>Access Constraints</i>	No	<i>license</i>	Yes
<i>Archive and Distribution Information</i>	No		No
<i>Direct Distribution Information</i>	No		No
<i>Publication Reference</i>	No		No
<i>ISO Topic Category</i>	No		No
Science Keywords	Yes		No
<i>Ancillary Keywords</i>	No	<i>keywords</i>	No
<i>Additional Attributes</i>	No		No
<i>Metadata Association</i>	No		No
<i>Temporal Extent</i>	No	<i>extent</i>	Yes
<i>Paleo Temporal Coverage</i>	No		No
<i>Temporal Keywords</i>	No		No
<i>Spatial Extent</i>	No	<i>extent</i>	Yes
<i>Tiling Identification System</i>	No		No
<i>Spatial Information</i>	No		No
<i>Location Keywords</i>	No		No

Platform	Yes	summaries-platform	No
Instrument	Yes	summaries-instruments	No
<i>Project</i>	<i>No</i>		<i>No</i>
Related URL	Yes	Links	No
Short Name	Yes		No
Version	Yes	stac_version	Yes
<i>Version Description</i>	<i>No</i>		<i>No</i>